

Psychro Cave

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Psychro Cave is located on the southern edge of the Plain of Lasithi in the Dikti Mountain Range of Crete. It sits at an elevation of 1025m above sea level and was the site of cult activity from the Bronze Age through to the Roman period. According to mythology, the cave was the birthplace of Zeus.

Date Range: 1900 BCE - 1000 CE

Region: Psychro Cave, Lasithi Plain

Region tags: Greece, Crete

The cave sanctuary of Psychro at the southern edge of the Lasithi Plain.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Hogarth, D. "The Dikti Cave," BSA 6 (1899-1900): 94-116.
- Source 2: Halbherr, F. "Scoperte nell'antro di Psychro," Museo Italiano di antichita Classica 2 (1888): 905-12.
- Source 3: Demargne, P. "Antiquites de Praesos et de l'antre dicteen," BCH 26 (1902): 571- 583.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Greek Ministry of Culture and Sports: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/eh251.jsp?obj_id=1628

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1886, 1896-1899

Notes: 1886: Hazzidakis and Halbherr excavated the entrance of the cave 1896: Arthur Evans excavated the upper chamber 1897: P. Demargne continued excavating the upper chamber 1899: David Hogarth was the first to systematically explore and excavate the cave.

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Yearly excavations took place by Hazzidakis and Halbherr (in 1886), Arthur Evans (in 1896), P. Demargne (in 1897), and David Hogarth (in 1899).

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Cave

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Terracing

Notes: A 50 m long terrace was created outside the entrance to the cave in the Late Minoan I period.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

Notes: The climb to the cave on the Lasithi Plain was probably part of the ritual activity associated with the site and with the act of pilgrimage to it.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– No

Notes: In the Bronze Age, there must have been roads connecting the Minoan settlements and palaces of the lower-lands to the higher elevation of the Lasithi Plain, but no obvious prehistoric roadways remain.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: The site is a single cave, but the cave consists of three separate components: a broad terrace outside the mouth of the cave, an upper chamber, and a lower cave.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Although evidence for the earliest human activity at the cave, in the Late Neolithic period, is found in both the lower cave and upper chamber, early Minoan remains are concentrated in the upper chamber. Kamares ware, for instance, was found only in the upper chamber. By the Neopalatial period, an altar and possible storeroom were erected in the north corner of this area. Although the space outside the mouth of the cave may have been utilized prior to the Neopalatial period, it wasn't until then that the monumental terrace was constructed.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Probably both.

Notes: The large terrace outside the mouth of the cave could have facilitated the gathering of large groups of people, making it possible to conduct communal worship at the cave, but the diversity of the material objects also suggests an individuality to the ritual activities. A lack of written records make it impossible to know for sure, but it is likely that both communal and individual worship took place at the site.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Although human habitation at the cave began in the Late Neolithic period, and ritual activity started in the early Protopalatial and continued through to the Roman period, a long-term use reflected in the array of material objects found at the site, the cave itself was not greatly modified through time. The main structural or architectural modifications were made in the Neopalatial period, when a large terrace of cyclopean masonry was constructed outside the mouth of the cave, and an altar and possible temenos area were built in the north corner of the upper chamber.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The cave itself has not been reconstructed, though modern additions of concrete steps and metal railings now lead the way into and out of the cave to facilitate visitors to the site.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Zeus/a young male god

Notes: The Psychro Cave is usually assumed to be the Dictaeon Cave, the mythological birthplace of Zeus first attested in "Theogony" (477-484) by Hesiod, and that it therefore functioned as a shrine to the god in his youth. A Linear B tablet from Knossos (Fp 1) records an offering of oil given to Dictaeon Zeus at a shrine most likely located in central Crete (Ventris and Chadwick 1973, 305-306); however, without the aid of additional written sources, it is difficult to confirm the precise location of this cult in the Bronze Age or the identification of the Psychro Cave's ritual activities. Indeed, archaeological evidence for Minoan cult makes it more likely that a young Cretan god was venerated at multiple cult sites across the island (Watrous 1996, 19), and that the Psychro Cave was just one of many sacred sites dedicated to Zeus or a Minoan forebearer of the Olympian. By the 8th-7th centuries BCE, Psychro was an important site, attracting religious dedications to Zeus from as far as Knossos, Corinth, and Egypt (Watrous 1996, 19), but it is unknown whether the epithet "Dictaeon" was attached to this particular cult at this time. By the Hellenistic period, the cult of Dictaeon Zeus was placed further east in Crete, not more centrally located in Lasithi.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that worshippers venerated more than one deity at Psychro Cave, but most evidence points to a focus on the cult of Zeus, or at least, a young male god.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ritual activity in the cave seems to focus on a supernatural being, most likely Zeus/a young male god, with little evidence for ancestor worship. It is, however, interesting to note that the Psychro sanctuary follows a tradition in which Minoan shrines were established in caves that had previously been inhabited, often in the Neolithic and Early Minoan periods (Watrous 1996, 81).

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Birthplace of high god

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Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: The origins of the cult seem to have grown organically from early Minoan cult traditions, perhaps, in part, commemorating the earlier habitation of the cave by ancestors in the Late Neolithic. No specific financial or material sponsor can be identified, though it is reasonable to assume that a large investment of wealth and resources was dedicated to the site in the Neopalatial period, when a broad terrace, altar, and possible temenos were constructed in the upper chamber and outside of the cave.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

Notes: The sacred site was probably established to commemorate the earlier habitation of ancestors in the Late Neolithic, and then grew to venerate the birthplace of Zeus or a powerful young male god.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The only monumental architecture at the site is part of the terrace outside the entrance to the cave. Here, an exterior terrace wall of Minoan construction runs for 40 m north-south and extends 4-5 m in width. Its outer (east) face is constructed of cyclopean masonry.

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since most of the site makes use of the natural features of the cave, the terrace is the only built monument at the site, and the percentage of the area which it covers is unknown. It should be noted that a Neopalatial storeroom is sometimes also included as a feature in the north corner of the cave's upper chamber. Although there is little architecture to be seen today, Hogarth (1899-1900, 105) believed that this part of the upper chamber had been paved with a stone floor and sectioned off by a temenos wall.

Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Notes: 40 m long (north-south) x 4-5 m wide

Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since most of the site makes use of the natural features of the cave, the terrace is the only built monument at the site, making it impossible to determine an average.

Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since most of the site makes use of the natural features of the cave, the terrace is the only built monument at the site, making it impossible to determine an average.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The cave cuts into the natural bedrock of the Lasithi Plain.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although the Psychro Cave is linked with the mythology of Zeus, the supreme high god of the twelve Olympian gods of Classical Greece, there is no evidence to suggest that Zeus was considered to be the supreme god in the Bronze Age. Indeed, the Bronze Age emphasis on female deities makes such a hierarchy unlikely, at least in the earlier periods of the cult. Given the continuation of ritual activity at the cave from the Bronze Age through to the Roman period, it can be assumed that a change in the pantheon occurred at some point in its history, but an exact moment is unknown. Furthermore, due to the lack of religious texts or historical writing, it is impossible to know if it was believed that Zeus or any other god was actually present in the cave, or if the ritual activity focused on the site was commemorating its importance in mythology (i.e. the birthplace of Zeus).

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It cannot be known for certain, though it is unlikely that human spirits were believed to be present considering the focus on mythological tradition.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: Despite the many anthropomorphic figurines found in the cave, none seem to be a cult statue

of a deity or supernatural being.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Evidence for animal sacrifice found around the altar in the upper chamber.

Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: The first bronze offerings, including daggers, votive double axes, small axheads, tweezers, and a votive foot, were left in the cave in the Protopalatial period. Two gold strips and jewellery beads also date to this period. In the Neopalatial, full-size daggers and miniature weapons were dedicated, as well as personal possessions including pins, rings, earrings, beads, sealstones, and strips of gold sewn on clothing. Weapons and jewellery continued to be dedicated at the cave until the end of the Archaic period.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Some are, including ceramic vessels and small personal possessions.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Notes: Offerings were left in the cave or scattered around the altar, but were not deposited in intentional pits or caches.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The location of the Psychro Cave would have made any visit to the site a considerable effort, and given the lack of nearby settlements, it is likely that the cave was a place of intentional ritual travel. Watrous (1996, 51) suggests that worshippers climbed the mountain to Psychro from their homes at Malia and the Lasithi area. The precise distances that were travelled would, however, have varied depending on where the visitor was coming from, and it is not possible to know whether or not a long trip or pilgrimage was a required part of the cave's cult practices.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The remains of oxen, pig, deer, and goats found scattered around the Neopalatial stuccoed altar in the upper chamber attest to the practice of animal sacrifice as well as ritual feasting in the cave.

Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Seems to have been concentrated in the upper chamber, for there is no evidence of food or libations in the lower chamber.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence of healing rituals or cult has been found at the Psychro cave (Watrous 1996, 72). While some of the material evidence found at peak sanctuaries, including terracotta models of limbs, torsoes, or body parts, and figurines possibly depicting childbirth, are thought to connect peak sanctuary ritual with healing practices, none of this same evidence was found at Psychro.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is impossible to know for certain, given the lack of written evidence or religious records, but it seems likely that the construction of the terrace in the Neopalatial period outside of the cave's entrance points to robust levels of cult participation. Watrous (1996, 51) suggests that the terrace may have been able to accommodate groups up to 250.

Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The material evidence points to the practice of small-scale rituals at Psychro, including the dedication of offerings and libations, practices of feasting, drinking, and offering of sacrifices.

- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: The field doesn't know, though Watrous (1996, 51) suggests that the terrace constructed outside of the cave's entrance in the Neopalatial period may have held up to 250 worshippers.
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Field doesn't know.
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Notes: Given the range of material remains found at the site, it seems unlikely that there were specific formal institutions used to maintain the cave, but because written records do not exist, it is not possible to rule out this possibility completely.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Bogdan Rutkowski , Krzysztof Nowicki. The Psychro Cave and Other Sacred Grottoes in Crete. Warsaw: The Polish Academy of Science.

Reference: David Hogarth George. The Dictaeon Cave.

Reference: L. Vance Watrous. The Cave Sanctuary of Zeus at Psychro: A Study of Extra-Urban Sanctuaries

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